

PERIGEO: IMAGE PROCESSING TECHNIQUES DEVELOPMENT & TESTING FOR MULTIMODAL ABSOLUTE & RELATIVE NAVIGATION

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ABSTRACT

PERIGEO is an R&D project, funded by the INNPRONTA 2011-2014 programme from Spanish CDTI, which aims to investigate the use of UAV technologies and processes for the validation of space oriented technologies. For this purpose, among different space missions and technologies, a set of activities for absolute and relative navigation are being carried out to deal with the attitude and position estimation problem from a temporal image sequence from a camera on the visible spectrum and/or Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) sensor. The process is covered entirely: from sensor measurements and data acquisition (images, LiDAR ranges and angles), data pre-processing (calibration and co-registration of camera and LIDAR data), features and landmarks extraction from the images and image/LiDAR-based state estimation.

The activities envisaged in PERIGEO cover the development and validation of algorithms and technology testing on UAVs under representative conditions. The first activity has been carried out through the use of synthetic measurement produced with different SW tools or existing (and representative) camera and LIDAR images databases. As an intermediate step between simulation and real environment, a tool named Dual-Synthetic Environment (DSE) has been developed, which allows system integration and testing for both software and hardware elements, under representative environmental conditions e.g. gravity, illumination, etc. The final step, currently under development, consists on migrating the algorithms to a compact hardware platform, including sensors, to be integrated in the UAV payload and tested on flight.

1. THE PERIGEO PROJECT

PERIGEO is an R&D project, funded by the INNPRONTA 2011-2014 programme from Spanish CDTI, and its goal is to create tools and methodologies that allow to continue the effort performed in laboratory (Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 3-4) for space systems developments, exposing the technology to environmental and dynamic conditions that can be considered representative, to a certain extent, of the ones encountered in the target scene mission (TRL 5-6). For this purpose, PERIGEO aims to investigate the use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technologies and processes for the validation of space oriented technologies.

Four different scenarios are considered in PERIGEO: Earth observation, interplanetary flight, atmospheric flight and *in-situ* exploration. According to the scenarios and the space missions defined for each one, the following challenges have been defined and will be afforded in PERIGEO:

- To define new **designs of missions and vehicles** by multidisciplinary optimization of its shape and configuration.
- To develop a **robust and failure-tolerant control system**.
- To define new **autonomous navigation** methods based on optical sensors and its hybridization.
- To study an **integrated research and design process** that allows the use of real time data to increase the system performance.

Within the broad scope of activities in PERIGEO, this paper focuses on the algorithmic and methodological developments for multi-modal i.e. absolute and relative navigation for the atmospheric flight scenario.

Mission scenario for autonomous navigation in PERIGEO: Atmospheric Flight on Titan

As mentioned earlier, one of the flight missions selected is an atmospheric flight on Titan, which is specially challenging on demonstrating robust estimation methods in real-time and within a difficult environment. Roughly speaking, the airplane should be capable of autonomously following a flight pattern specified by the ground control within a given precision; therefore, the airplane shall be capable of determining its position by combining measurements from suitable on-board sensors.

Further in detail, the Titan mission scenario design is explained herein. The airplane reaches Titan, stored inside a dedicated Entry Vehicle (EV) and connected to a Space Vehicle (SV), mainly responsible for the interplanetary phase propulsion. The entry vehicle separates from the space vehicle once a final direct entry targeting maneuver has been performed. Once the parachute has been deployed (at an altitude ranging from 150 to 200 km), the EV slowly descends down to an altitude of 40 km. At this altitude, the airplane is released and the atmospheric science operations start. While sloping from its deployment altitude of 40 km down to the nominal cruise altitude, the airplane can measure the upper troposphere of Titan. When the nominal cruise altitude is reached, the nominal operation phase starts, which is expected to last around one year. A nominal cruise altitude of 8 km would be a good candidate for science operations, since it enables ground imaging resolutions of few-meter Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) with applicable hardware, which is coherent with actual mission requirements. After that, climb-and-glide maneuvers are performed while downloading data to the ground stations i.e. Earth, as depicted in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Atmospheric Flight on Titan Mission Profile

In view of the latter, and in relation to navigation, the main requirements and challenges for this scenario can be summarized as the need for real time processing techniques, Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) unavailability e.g. GPS, the use of vision- and LIDAR-aided inertial navigation, and combined relative and absolute navigation.

Research and Design Integrated Process

One of the objectives of PERIGEO is to research on procedures to perform tests of complex space-systems in different environments, from functional engineering simulation to near-real conditions, while reducing costs and development time. The Dual Synthetic Environment (i.e. ESD) facility is devised as a tool or method to fulfil the mentioned needs, specially related with the maturation of different technologies such as GNC/AOCS, GNSS, Image Processing, etc.

The capacity to design, develop and test “Flight Systems” could be used in these areas to introduce their specific solutions for flying a real system and to test their maturity, stability and qualities. It could be used as well as a means to test new solutions in real environments, demonstrating the validity of the proposals and their adequacy for final implementation in a production phase. The ESD could be used also as a means to raise the TRL level of the engineering solutions, as well as to test and evolve product solutions or ideas, in order to evaluate their possible introduction in the market.

The complete production chain of the ESD is shown in a schematic view in Figure 2, starting from the design of the system and finalizing in the analysis of the flight tests.

Fig. 2: Production chain of the ESD

Testing on real flight campaigns

As stated before, PERIGEO aims to increase the TRL level up to 5-6 by using UAV technologies for testing the systems developed. Several UAV flight campaigns have been defined to test technologies and scenarios under representative space conditions.

For this purpose, the main requirements at system and subsystem level have been extracted from the space missions and evaluate their restriction level and scalability. As an example, the LIDAR selection has been done based on its resolution, which is a key aspect on the technology and the scenario to be tested, and its cost. As a consequence, other requirements such as the range have been biased, but can be interpreted as a scale problem (increasing the range is feasible by increasing the cost, while the technology developed is not affected).

2. VISIONA: IMAGE AND LIDAR PROCESSING FOR SPACE ENVIRONMENTS

A. CONCEPT, HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE AND COMPONENTS

The VISIONA system has been designed in PERIGEO with the ultimate goal of providing inputs to a platform's GNC module and a Hazard Detection and Avoidance (HDA) module, acting as an intermediate piece of the whole mission chain. To do so, on one hand VISIONA is required to perform multi-modal navigation, that is, either in a relative or absolute mode. Coarsely, *relative* navigation refers to the propagation of the navigation states (that is, time-position-velocity-attitude, tPVA) expressed in a convenient reference frame e.g. global, local surface-attached, or local instrumental, between two epochs in which *absolute* navigation has been performed, that is, states have been estimated using external absolute information such as previously geo-referenced grounds landmarks when available. In summary, *relative* navigation is the 'only thing you can do' when no *absolute* navigation is possible. On the other hand, VISIONA uses LiDAR technology for environment perception by deriving elevation/terrain models, and aims to relate the LiDAR-derived information to the camera images, that is, to perform camera and LiDAR co-registration. The surface models and registered images are valuable inputs for HDA tasks.

As already inferred from last paragraph, the main sensors in VISIONA are visible-spectrum cameras and LiDAR technology. It is worth to mention that other tasks within PERIGEO deal with the processing of IMU and GNSS for navigation adapted to space-like fault-tolerant architectures, and thus no other auxiliary sensors as Inertial Measurement Units (IMU), barometers, magnetometers, etc. are used in the current prototype (discussion on potential benefits of inertial- and vision-based combined navigation is held further on). Additionally, and in order to approach realistic space mission developments as a principal goal in PERIGEO, the designed algorithms and methods shall be austere in terms of computational burden, mirroring on-board GNC systems, and the scalability of the system shall be studied and characterized to propose upgrades of technology TRL.

Figure 3 shows the high-level architecture designed for VISIONA, expressed as a sequential chain of concatenated algorithms, following a coarse pipeline, 'measurement sources'-'feature management'-'estimators' (depicted in blue, orange and green colors in the figure). More in detail, in the event of a new camera image, VISIONA firstly pre-processes it to extract relevant features such as distinctive points and craters on the surface. In addition to the extraction, points are matched between consecutive, overlapping images and craters are matched against a set of pre-extracted craters from existing coordinated cartography of the surface. These

two types of elements are the ‘measurements’ to perform state estimation, that is, navigation. Next, the update in navigation is used to derive a motion-corrected and re-gridded terrain model from the LiDAR measurements. Again craters are extracted (now, from the digital terrain model) as distinctive features, and matched to those previously extracted from camera images. By doing so, the relative geometry between the terrain model and the camera image is estimated and, thus, camera and LiDAR images are co-registered (note that we will use the concept of ‘LiDAR image’ hereafter to refer to the 2.5D image constructed from the planimetric coordinates of the LiDAR ground points and the height component as ‘pixel intensity’).

VISIONA has been implemented following the Object-Oriented paradigm in C++, and according to two modalities of usage: the *offline* modality, in which camera images and LiDAR range-angle measurements (either coming from real or simulated sensors) are input in file format, and the *online* modality, in which the software is prepared to read from actual interfaced sensors in a CPU board. The development has been driven by time- and accuracy-performance compatibility to GNC demands, and also driven by user flexibility to define the principal sensor characteristics. To benefit from low-level handling and processing of data structures, specially of images, the OpenCV image processing library [1] has been integrated in the SW development.

Finally, in order to tailor algorithm development towards real space environments, the Planet and Asteroid Natural Scene Generation Utility (PANGU) has been used to obtain simulated optical images and digital elevation models from the Moon [2].

Fig. 3: VISIONA high-level architecture

[Robust] point extraction, description and matching

The first step after a camera image is available is to extract features of interest, such as distinctive points. A large set of literature is available on this topic, resulting in a myriad of methods to perform such task, as reviewed in [3]. In VISIONA, BRISK-based extraction and description is performed to maximize the number of extracted points while keeping computational burden low.

The result of a pair of processed overlapping images is shown in figure 4 (top), where a mixture of correct and incorrect matchings is depicted. Current validation activities within the project have revealed a ratio of less than 50% of correct matchings in Moon-like images. This is clearly problematic for statistical analysis: it is well known that the maximum breakdown point achievable by any statistical estimator in 0.5, and thus an alternative appropriate strategy is required. For that purpose, the following method is implemented: after extracting and matching image points, a prediction of the orientation of the second image is performed –this is feasible because the first image is already oriented, and linear and angular velocities may be inferred from ‘naïve’ motion ($\dot{v} = 0, \dot{\Omega} = 0$) or, more accurately, input by external sensors such as IMU. Then, by computing a coplanarity-related index for each pair of matched points, outliers and inliers are clearly separated (figure 4, bottom). Robust statistical analysis based on median and median variance estimators is applied to the inlier set to clean few ‘coplanarity-transparent’ outliers.

Fig. 4: Extracted distinctive points from a pair of overlapping images (top); inlier (bottom, left) and outlier (bottom, down) classification

Camera and LiDAR crater extraction

Comprehensive literature exists in relation to the identification of craters in planetary imagery [4]. In PERIGEO, craters are just features from which suitable information is derived to perform navigation, and other scientific goals such as the study of crater density, distribution or morphology fall beyond the project scope. Thus, computational efficiency, robustness to illumination conditions and visible/LiDAR independency were primary requirements for the crater extraction algorithm among others.

For camera images, the followed approach is based on detecting the brightest and darkest areas of an image by simple thresholding techniques. To maximize 'black' and 'white' area detection, a cascade of BlackHat and TopHat morphological operators are applied respectively before thresholding, varying the size of the structuring element to account for different crater sizes and to provide invariance against scale changes. The result of properly averaging the output images is processed in search of contours of black and white areas. Finally, these contours are merged and filtered according to size, proximity and roundness of each 'black-white' pair. A result of this processing chain is shown in figure 5, using PANGU images with Sun elevation of 5°. Validation results have shown stability on crater extraction for Sun elevation values between 1° and 10°.

Fig. 5: Original image (left), extracted white/black areas in red/green (center) and final crater identification

LiDAR images are independent of illumination conditions, what translates in a higher repeatability in crater extraction, and thus a better technology candidate to use for this purpose. The approach in VISIONA consists on applying derivative Sobel operators in the x and y image-axis directions and combine its output (indeed, a crater responds similarly to such an operator in any direction). The resulting images are equalized and conveniently threshold to extract regions with gradient variation. After contour extraction to the threshold images, final crater identification is performed by merging contours according to size, proximity and alignment with respect to the image axis. Figure 6 shows a result of LiDAR crater extraction chain, using the associated digital terrain model from the previous PANGU image (figure 5).

Fig. 6: Original image (top, left), Sobel derivative (top, right), gradient image (bottom, left) and final crater identification (bottom, right)

Crater description and matching

In order to identify crater correspondences in two different images containing N and M craters, a descriptor for triplets of craters has been designed with resiliency to scale and relative orientation between the source images. Each descriptor encapsulates information on the areas and distances between centroids of a crater triplet. Both areas and distances are duly normalized to achieve resiliency to scale changes. Finally, each triplet incorporates area-based crater ordination.

Once built, the descriptors are compared against each other and, if its distance is below a certain threshold, a vote is assigned to each individual crater. By doing so, a confusion matrix of dimension $N \times M$ is built containing in each cell $c_{i,j}$ the number of votes associated to the statement 'the i -th crater corresponds to the j -th crater'. The analysis of the full matrix provides a reliability figure of merit to each match, which is used to discard low-probable matchings. This technique is implemented in VISIONA to be used for camera-to-pre-extracted crater matching for absolute navigation, as well as camera-to-LiDAR crater matching for co-registration.

Relative and Absolute Navigation

Under the perspective of navigation, the previously described components are ‘measurement providers’. Indeed, the goal of the previous components is to *measure* in the image space some quantities of interest, and express those metrically in the object or image space. For example, the point extractor, descriptor and matcher delivers coordinates in the image-space of the points; and the crater extractor, descriptor and matcher delivers coordinates of the crater centroids (2D coordinates in the case of image craters, and 3D coordinates in the case of LiDAR craters).

For relative navigation, suppose that at time t_n , an image I_n is obtained from a sensor. Then, the point extractor, descriptor and matcher component provides a set of paired image pixels $\{(x, y)_n^i, (x, y)_{n-1}^i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$ from image I_n and previous image I_{n-1} (suppose that these matches have already been ‘cleaned’ by the outlier removal procedure). As a prediction of the current orientation is available, i.e. $(\tilde{P}_n, \tilde{\Omega}_n)$, it is used to derive ground coordinates $(\tilde{X}, \tilde{Y}, \tilde{Z})_i$ of the pair $(x, y)_n^i \leftrightarrow (x, y)_{n-1}^i$ by *space forward intersection*. Whenever a new image I_{n+1} is available, and new image points are matched $\{(x, y)_{n+1}^i, (x, y)_n^i\}_{i=1, \dots, M}$, then the pairs $(x, y)_{n+1}^i \leftrightarrow (\tilde{X}, \tilde{Y}, \tilde{Z})_i$ are used to estimate an orientation prediction $(\tilde{P}_{n+1}, \tilde{\Omega}_{n+1})$ by *space resection*. At that point, a bundle adjustment is performed to provide final estimates $(P_{n+1}, \Omega_{n+1}), \{(X, Y, Z)_i\}_{i=1, \dots, M}$ using any available related image, ground and/or orientation measurements, that is, $\{(x, y)_n^i, \dots, (x, y)_{n-k+1}^i\}_{i=1, \dots, N_1 + \dots + N_k}, \{(X, Y, Z)_j\}_{j=1, \dots, N_1 + \dots + N_k}$ and $(P_n, \Omega_n), \dots, (P_{n-k+1}, \Omega_{n-k+1})$. Note that the final expression considers not just triplets of images, but k-overlapping images.

The previously described procedure (or some sub-components of it) is usually referred as Structure From Motion (SfM) or visual odometry among the robotics and computer vision community –hereafter, we use the generic term ‘Iterative Bundle Adjustment’. Note that, in absence of sensors to provide ‘dynamic’ or ‘absolute’ measurements, such as IMU or GNSS, monocular camera navigation based on essential matrix estimation i.e. 2D-2D image-space measurements, does not enable to retrieve the absolute scale of the problem [5]. Therefore, the introduction of ground points as unknowns of the problem permits global scale estimation.

Absolute navigation, also known as exterior orientation problem or Perspective n-Point (PnP), is, again, a problem to be solved by space resection. In this case, the measurements are derived from a set of N matched craters, those extracted from image I_n at time t_n and those extracted from available coordinated cartography of the planet surface. More in detail, the input measurements are $\{(x, y)_n^i, (X, Y, Z)_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$, being $(x, y)_n^i$ the pixel coordinates of the centroid of the i -th extracted crater from image I_n , and $(X, Y, Z)_i$ the ground coordinates of the centroid of the i -th extracted crater from surface imagery, expressed in a surface-related coordinate frame. The space resection problem in VISIONA is approached as described in [6].

Motion Correction and Re-Gridding

The generation of terrain models is performed at each event of image reception. Thus, at epoch t_n , the set of LiDAR measurements $\{t_{n-1} < t < t_n, (t_i, \rho_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$ is transformed into a set of ground points $\{(X, Y, Z)_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$ by means of ray projection using the current and past position and attitude estimations $(P_{n-1}, \Omega_{n-1}), (P_n, \Omega_n)$. This process is usually known as *Motion Correction*. Note that using the position and attitude estimation at epoch t_n leads to more accurate results, yet a prediction based on the navigation states at t_{n-1} would enable independency and potential parallelization of motion correction and state estimation.

The *Re-Gridding* process deals with the generation of a dense and regularly-gridded ground model, based on the previous sparse set $\{(X, Y, Z)_i\}_{i=1, \dots, N}$. Actually, the re-gridded terrain model is a set of points of the form $\{(X_0 + i \cdot \Delta_X, Y_0 + j \cdot \Delta_Y, Z_{i,j})\}_{i=1, \dots, N_1, j=1, \dots, N_2}$ and with all points lying within the convex hull of the sparse set. To do so, a Delaunay triangulation is created based on the sparse set. This triangulation encapsulates proximity information, enabling to recover the three nearest neighbor points given a random query, that is, the triangle to which the point belongs to. In this way, height is deduced by simple inverse-distance weighting interpolation for any point in space. The re-gridded terrain model is used as a ‘LiDAR image’ to perform crater extraction, and is generally generated at a lower frequency than the motion-correction procedure.

Finally, note that an ancillary software module is used to extract LiDAR range-angle measurements from the PANGU digital terrain models. Current prototype for UAV testing considers measurements from a laser scanner, already delivering range-angle measurements, and therefore interface homogenization has been a key requirement to ease migration to the on-board prototype.

B. RESULTS

In order to present the results, a trajectory has been designed to be input to PANGU and, thus, obtain camera images and terrain models. The trajectory is a 1.3 kilometer-long linear trajectory towards North, featuring a descent from 600 meters to 300 meters and ascending again to 420 meters above terrain. In addition, the trajectory contains positive and negative turns in roll and heading, up to 17 and 30 degrees respectively. Figure 7 depicts the trajectory: on the left, a 3D plot for east-north-height positions, and on the right, the angle variations over time expressed in heading, pitch and roll (red, green and blue) parametrization.

Fig. 7: (left), 3D plot for east-north-height positions; (right), angle variations over time (heading, pitch and roll)

Figure 8 shows a sequence of images obtained with the trajectory. As a part of the setup, some craters have been pre-extracted and ground coordinates of its centroids have been measured, in order to test VISIONA's absolute navigation procedure. To do so, the software automatically extracts craters from the sequence of camera images and tries to match those against the pre-extracted craters. If successful, VISIONA prepares the 2D-3D measures and performs space resection. The middle image in figure 8 shows the craters pre-extracted for absolute navigation in red.

Fig. 8: Image sequence from the test trajectory. The middle image shows the pre-extracted craters to be used for absolute navigation.

Finally, in order to minimize the number of outliers in point matching, an IMU-based relative orientation of consecutive image pairs is used. In order to work under realistic assumptions, the characteristics of a real spaceborne IMU (particularly, the LN200S IMU from Northrop-Grumman, used in a wide range of current space missions) have been used in the processing. This corresponds to applying Gaussian noises $N(0, 0.05)$ for the relative position (in meters), $N(0, 0.008)$ and $N(0, 0.07)$ for the roll/pitch and heading angles, respectively (in degrees). We note that the IMU-related information is used solely in the outlier rejection procedure, and not in the state estimation step, which is performed as explained in the 'Relative and Absolute Navigation' section.

Figure 9 shows the multi-modal navigation results of the processed trajectory. Clearly, errors in the North and East components are correlated with pitch and roll errors, respectively (this effect is due to the linear motion of the vehicle towards North). When analyzing the particularities of this trajectory, we note that the actual relative attitude variations are quite large, e.g. relative roll between pair 10-11 is of 17 degrees, relative heading between pairs 12-13 and 13-14 is of 15 degrees, and relative heading between 14-15 and 15-16 is of 30 degrees. These are challenging maneuvers in which navigation quality is degraded. However, errors in pitch and roll (and, consequently, north and east) may be conveniently mitigated by a full integration IMU/camera, as these states can be better observed through accelerometers' measurements of gravity. The full integration of both sensors is a goal in PERIGEO, and current developments are undergoing to be able to test such integration in real flights with UAVs.

However, it is also clear in the figure that, in the epochs where absolute navigation is performed (images 7,8 and 16), errors are mitigated conveniently. More in detail, crater matching is successful in images 7, 8 and 16 (9 craters matched in the first two images, and 6 craters in the third), and thus absolute navigation is performed. Actually, craters are also matched in images 5 and 9 to some of the pre-extracted craters –yet, the matching includes some outliers producing large errors in space resection. When this happens, VISIONA automatically discards the information in order to continuously provide a valid solution.

Fig. 9: Position and attitude accuracy results for multi-modal navigation

3. PROTOTYPES AND REAL ENVIRONMENT TESTING

Project testing is a key component in PERIGEO, as the project seeks to increase the TRL of the developed technologies using UAVs as a means for this purpose. Genuine space sensors and systems are not available within the project –thus, the scalability and restrictions of the previously discussed requirements have been analyzed and appropriate technologies have been selected to be tested in-flight. As an example, the selected LiDAR sensor (Hokuyo UTM-30LX) features a short scanning range, yet this is regarded as a ‘scale problem’ in which cost and performance are clearly correlated. In this case, modulating the mission flying altitude enables the use of LiDAR within the project.

Figure 10 shows particular developments within PERIGEO. On the left, a Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) CPU board is displayed, in which VISIONA software is migrated to be tested in real flight conditions, and on the center, an AVT Prosilica GC2450 camera and Hokuyo UTM-30LX LiDAR are shown, as measurement sources for VISIONA. Finally, on the right, the UAV to be used for project testing is the SIVA, a fixed-wing platform developed by Instituto Nacional de Tecnologia Aeroespacial (INTA), featuring 300 kg of MTOW, 6 hours of endurance, a maximum speed of 170 km/h, and able to carry 40 kg of payload.

Fig. 10: VISIONA board (left); AVT Prosilica GC2450 and Hokuyo UTM-30LX sensors (center); INTA's UAV SIVA (right)

Project testing, scheduled within 2014, will be conducted around a controlled and segregated area around a take-off and landing site in which SIVA is authorized to manoeuvre e.g. regional airports. Depending on the final testing site, identifying analogies with outer space scenarios is not straight-forward, and therefore, special preparation of the test site is mandatory to include space-like elements i.e. craters. Further testing shall consider areas with a high-degree of likeliness with the Moon or other bodies of interest.

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